

ISic3159

Inscribed block of uncertain purpose

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 1332

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Fines
2. Vib (i)
3. Sever (i)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Translation (it)

Commentary

See ISic0306 for the inscription on the other side.

Digital identifiers:

TM 565496

EDR 140104

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7022b (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 035b

Manganaro, G. 1961. Ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. I. Per la storia del culto delle divinità orientali in Sicilia. *Siculorum Gymnasium.* 14: 175-198. At 192-194 ph

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 30 tav.8

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3159. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357216>